

Education Problems in Nigeria: Implications for Decision Making

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Abstract: The paper discusses the various problems hindering education development in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper. It employed a systematic literature review-based method. Previous literature from both online publications and print sources was reviewed. Content analysis was adopted to select the final literature used in the paper. The paper reveals that poor funding, shortage of professional teachers, infrastructure facilities, insecurities, corruption, lack of current data for planning and appointment of non-professionals to head educational institutions are some of the major problems facing education in Nigeria. Based on these findings, the paper recommends among other things that: there should be an increment in the budgetary allocation to education, employment of adequate professional teachers, provision of modern infrastructure facilities, provision of adequate security in schools, deployment of technologies to curtail corruption in the education administration, generation of timely data for educational planning and appointment of professional and qualified persons to head educational institutions.

Keywords: Funding, Education, School, Teachers.

Introduction

The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) provides a guide to attempting to fulfil the nation's objectives. This notion has five major objectives as stated in the Second National Development Plan namely:- 1) a free and democratic society, 2) a just and egalitarian society, 3) a united strong and self-reliant nation, 4) a great and dynamic economy, and 5) a land of bright and full of opportunities for all citizens.

Education concerns the individual and society. It is the act of systematic development or training of the mind, capabilities or character through instruction or study. Education varies as widely in its forms, philosophy, contents, and methods as there are different societies in the world. Education is a life-long process that has interpretation in purpose, type and level. It is a means of socializing people into the community, for upholding customs and traditions as well as for the modification or changing of same in conformity with existing ideologies, ideological expansion or reformation (NOUN, 2013).

Nigerian educational system comprises early child education, basic education, senior secondary school education and tertiary education. In Nigeria, governments at all levels have adopted

education as an instrument for the attainment of national development. Education is an instrument for effecting national development. Education can be defined as the production and reproduction of knowledge of people's way of life (i.e. their culture) to preserve and maintain the social structure that will be able to guarantee social order and changes in society (NOUN, 2013). Training as one of the end products of education entails improving the performance of individuals on their jobs by correcting any deficiency in human effort (Ogunode & Ayeni, 2023).

Education in Nigeria appears to be facing numerous problems. Peter (2015) pointed out that Nigeria's educational dilemmas stemmed from politicizing educational issues whereby much attention is been paid to personal, sentiment and other primordial issues. Politicizing education is a serious problem for educational policy implementation. It is based on this that this paper seeks to discuss the problems facing education in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Education is a process that transfers knowledge, skills, and character traits that come or manifest in various forms to empower the individual to be socially and economically useful to himself or herself and society. Education is an organized and planned process that leads to the acquisition of knowledge from an institute of learning for personal and national development (Ogunode, Solomon, & Idonigie, 2024). Education is a strong tool for individual and national development. It is the process of developing people to be self-reliant and contribute meaningfully to the development of the nation. It involves the acquisition of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and competencies needed to be responsible. Education tends to promote socioeconomic, political and technological improvement in a country (Fasasi & Ijaiya, 2017). Education is the acquisition of knowledge that tends to train and develop the individual. Education embraces not only school experiences but also indirect or incidental influences which help us to learn, such influences and activities affect our character, behaviours and perceptions (Emenike 2004).

Education is the process by which individuals are selected and assigned social roles while the second shows that the level of development in a society is dependent on the type (or quality) of education given to its members. All in all, education is a continuous learning process through which members of a society acquire the requisite knowledge and skills to facilitate the effective performance of assigned social responsibilities (NOUN, 2012). Education is so important in the life of human society that access to it can empower people to provide for their basic needs (Ayeni, Sani, Idris, & Uzoigwe, 2019). Not only that, the role of education is so important that having low-level access to it has resulted in the absence of popular participation and involvement in the decision-making of government (Ayeni, 2017). There is a need for education to be prioritised for national development.

Methods

This paper is a review paper. It employed a systematic literature review-based method. Previous literature from both online publications and print sources was reviewed. Content analysis was used to select secondary information on this topic. The method adopted followed a systematic review process-based narrative design. The first process began by sourcing materials online and in print materials identified, downloaded and collected. The second step involves the selection and organization of literature that has a direct link to the topic. The previous findings are critically analyzed and presented in different themes on the importance of educational laws in enhancing quality education in tertiary institutions.

Data Analysis on Education Problems in Nigeria

There are many investigations on problems facing the Nigerian educational system. For instance, Nuhu (2024) identified poor funding. Funding is critical to the development of education. Funding is the pillars that aid the transformation of education. Unfortunately, for the past two decades, the budgetary allocation to education in Nigeria has been below the

recommendations of UNESCO.

Year	Budget	Education Allocation	%
1999	407bn(\$18.59bn)	34.4bn(\$1.57bn)	– 8.45%
2000	702bn(\$8.16bn)	37.48bn(\$435.99m)	– 5.34%
2001	1.318trn(\$13.31bn)	62.636bn(\$632.69m)	– 4.75%
2002	1.0648trn(\$9.77bn)	61.36bn(\$562.94m)	– 5.76%
2003	1.45trn(\$12.72bn)	21.503bn(\$188.62m)	– 1.48%
2004	1.3trn(\$10.24bn) 1	15.5bn(\$909/45m)	– 8.88%
2005	1.8trn(\$14.01bn) 1	30.2bn(\$986.36m)	– 7.23%
2006	1.88trn(\$14.63bn)	202.4bn(\$1.575bn)	– 10.77%
2007	2.39trn(\$19.92bn)	180.407bn(\$1.503bn)	– 7.55%
2008	2.74trn(\$23.03bn)	268.84bn(\$2.326bn)	– 9.81%
2009	3.049trn(\$21.03bn)	199.405bn(\$1.375bn)	– 6.54%
2010	5.160trn(\$34.4bn)	249.09bn(\$1.661bn)	– 4.83%
2011	4.972trn(\$33.15bn)	306.30bn(\$2.042bn)	– 6.16%
2012	5.0386trn(\$32.93bn)	400.15bn(\$2.615bn)	– 7.94%
2013	4.987trn(\$31.17bn)	426.53bn(\$2.666bn)	– 8.55%
2014	5.230trn(\$32.67bn)	493bn(\$3.081bn)	– 9.43%
2015	5.6425trn(\$29.67bn)	392bn(\$2.062bn)	– 6.95%
2016	6.061trn(\$30.74bn)	369.60bn(\$1.875bn)	– 6.10%
2017	7.441trn(\$24.40bn)	550bn(\$1.803bn)	– 7.39%
2018	9.12trn(\$29.25bn)	605.80bn(\$1.986bn)	– 6.64%
2019	8.92trn(29.42bn)	620.50bn(\$2.034bn)	– 6.96%
2020	10.59trn(\$29.42bn)	691.07bn(\$1.920bn)	– 6.53%
2021	14.573trn(\$38.45bn)	1.2126trn(\$3.199bn)	– 8.32%
2022	17.908trn(\$43.66bn)	1.234trn(\$3.010bn)	– 6.89%
2023	24.007bn(\$55.10bn)	1.54trn(\$3.5345bn)	– 6.41%
2024	35.055trn(\$43.82bn)	2.18trn(\$2.725bn)	– 6.22%
2025	49.74trn(\$33.16bn)	3.52trn(\$2.347bn)	– 7.08%
27yrs	232.546trn(\$667.887bn)	16.105trn(\$49.641bn)	– 6.93%

In the last 27 years, **Ndujihe, C. (2024)** noted that the education sector received a cumulative 6.93 per cent of the budget, which is far below the recommended benchmarks of Nigeria, the World Bank, and the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation, UNESCO. UNESCO recommends that national and subnational governments should devote 26 per cent of their budgets to education. The World Bank recommends 20 to 30 per cent while Nigeria's National Policy on Education provides that not less than 26 per cent of Federal and state governments' budgets should be allocated to education. The non-prioritisation of education has made scholars note that there is a failure of leadership in Nigeria (Ayeni, 2018).

Another problem in education is the shortage of professional teachers. Teachers are the implementers of the school curriculum. Their functions include teaching, preparing lesson notes and lesson plans, evaluating the students, setting exam questions and marking answer sheets. Their functions also include providing leadership in classes, performing academic services, relating with parents on feedback on students' progress and sometimes carrying students on excursions with school permission. Teachers are very important factors in the management of educational institutions, especially secondary schools. The teachers' roles

cannot be replaced in delivering of teaching programme (Ogunode 2021). It is unfortunate that as important as the teachers are to achieve the education objectives they are not adequate. Punch (2024) reports that **in the 2022-2023 Universal Basic Education Commission National Personnel Audit report, the commission said there is a shortage of 194,876 teachers in public primary schools across the country. In 2022, the National Universities Commission said 100,000 faculties were attending to 2.1 million undergraduates. Comparatively, there were 16,000 staff and faculty, including 2,400 professors, lecturers, and instructors at Harvard as of then. The shortage of teachers has been attributed to a situation where** a structure is not performing its function optimally (Joseph, Cinjel & Ayeni, 2017; Ayeni & Nwaorgu, 2018). Ejike, and Ejike, (2018) **noted that both senior secondary schools and tertiary institutions in Nigeria are facing the problem of a shortage of professional teachers.** Okeke (2024) observed that Nigeria is facing a critical shortage of qualified teachers to manage its primary and secondary schools in both urban and rural areas. This lack of enough trained educators to meet the needs of the students, especially in the rural areas where resources are scarce has continued to be the bane of quality learning as most schools have to do with unqualified persons to man the available schools. The shortage of teachers has been attributed to poor salaries, welfare, poor working materials and environment, and poor recognition among others.

Shortage of infrastructure facilities is another problem in the management of education in Nigeria. Infrastructural facilities according to Ogunode (2020) are those facilities aiding the delivery of academic and non-academic services in educational institutions. Infrastructural facilities include; libraries, laboratories, halls, offices, administrative blocks, hostels, road facilities, water, electricity, internet et cetera. Infrastructure is germane because it provides long-term satisfaction (Ayeni, Doosuur, & Kefas, 2021). For Ehiametalor (2001), infrastructure is the operational input of every instructional programme and constitutes elements that are necessary for teaching and learning. Such include buildings, laboratories, machinery, furniture and electrical fixtures. These must be functional about other aspects of the community, such as health centres, libraries, and good roads and must be large enough to allow for expansion as enrolments expand. The importance of infrastructural facilities in educational institutions according to Ogunode and Agwor (2021) include; aiding the effective delivery of administrative functions in schools; making the delivery of services fast and reliable; enabling teachers to deliver lessons fast; infrastructural facilities provide a conducive working environment for both teachers and students; infrastructural facilities enable learners to learn at ease and learn well; infrastructural facilities enable the teachers to teach well, prepare their lessons, and deliver them online (ICT). The importance of school infrastructural facilities in the realization of educational goals cannot be underestimated. School facilities aid the delivery of the teaching and learning process in the schools. The school offices provide a conducive working environment for teachers, the classrooms help the learners to learn while the school fence protects students, the teachers, and school administrators from criminals. The school plant protects the entire human resources from the sun, rain, heat cold, and snow (Ogunode & Agwor 202; Ebehikhalu, & Dawam 2016). Infrastructure facilities are key to the smooth implementation of the curriculum in higher institutions. Peter, (2017) observed that in the majority of Nigeria schools, the classroom accommodation is grossly inadequate as a result of the large enrolments in these schools, the classrooms are usually overcrowded, with up to sixty or more students receiving classroom instructions designed for only thirty or, forty students. In most cases, the chairs and desks are not enough; you see them sharing chairs, standing up, or sitting on windows or broken desks. When students are overcrowded like this, there is a stalling of the teaching-learning process and a disruption of the children's mental activity, a situation that generally militates against the effective teaching and intellectual development of the children. The non-provision of infrastructure has been attributed to the provision of stomach infrastructure that cannot bring about sustainable development (Ayeni, Tusayi, Joseph & Obatayo, 2018).

Insecurity problems also hinder the development of education in Nigeria. Effective School management cannot be possible in an unsecured environment. Thus, infrastructural development enhances human security (Ayeni, Andeshi, & Uzoigwe, 2022). Nigeria as a country is battling with insecurity challenges and this is affecting the entire educational institutions. This has made scholars call for.. Public secondary schools seem to be the most targeted sector of educational institutions in the country. The insecurity problem in Nigeria has led to the killing of students, teachers and school administrators. Many school infrastructural facilities have been destroyed by the insurgents. Ahmadu (2016); Ogunode, Ahaotu and Obi-E, (2021); Ogunode, and Ukozor (2022); Ogunode and Chijindu, (2022) discovered that the Boko Haram insurgency has led to developmental challenges through the destruction of lives and property and, the destruction of schools which has led to the closing down of so many schools which has affected the performance of students in such areas and destruction in business, reduction in government revenue, and political instability among others in the northeastern part of the country. Education is worst hit by the Boko Haram activities. This has been attributed to the failure of leadership in Nigeria (Ayeni, 2018; Ogunode 2021b).

Corruption is a very big problem in the administration and management of education in Nigeria. Ogunode (2021) noted that funds released by the government for the administration of the schools sometimes ended up in the private hands. Funds meant for the capital and recurrent services in the schools are been diverted by the officials of the ministries. Thus, scholars have noted that corruption in Nigeria has been a source of worry and has affected sustainable development (Amaechi, Ayeni, & Madu, 2019; Ayeni & Sani, 2021; Ogunode & Johnson, 2021). Funds budgeted for different programmes in the ministries are been diverted into private banks. Public funds meant for the development of education in Nigeria are diverted and mismanaged. Osunyanmi, (2018) Ogunode, Josiah, & Ajape, (2021); Ogunode, and Stephen, (2021) concluded that Nigeria has been experiencing underwhelming development amidst overwhelming corruption. Education is not insulated from this malaise. Corruption allows a high percentage of the funds allocated to the sector to get diverted into the private accounts of public officials. Hence, the amount being spent on education is much lower than the figure in the budget. In 2020, Transparency International maintained in their annual report that 66 per cent of the money the Nigerian governments allocates to education is stolen by corrupt officials. According to the report, corruption is commonplace in education systems across the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS, n.d; Premium Times, 2020). The foregoing is corroborated by scholars who noted that corruption has led to the underdevelopment of the education sector in Nigeria (Ayeni, & Andeshi, 2023).

The lack of data for effective planning and decision-making is another challenge in education management in Nigeria. Ogunode (2021) opined that the lack of current data on education is also posing a challenge to the effective management of secondary schools in Nigeria. Educational manager needs current data to plan and make decisions. Data helps educational managers to act fast and achieve results. It has been observed by Ogunode, (2021) that inadequate data is frustrating the planning of secondary schools in Nigeria. (NEEDS 2014) and Ogunode, Olowonefa and Idowu, (2024) submitted that it was challenging to obtain data with current statistics for the assessment mainly because current data on the education sector was generally not available in the public domain. The assessment therefore relied on available data, some of which were more than three years old and had not been updated at the time of the study (British Council, 2014; Ogunode, & Usman, 2023). Deployment of Educational Management Informati agreed that access to reliable and complete information on education in Nigeria has for a long time proved difficult. The development of a national database for education statistics has been slow and various data-generating agencies (including the Federal Ministry of Education, Universal Basic Education Commission, National Population Commission and National Bureau of Statistics) often used different sample designs, methods of data collection, analysis and reporting, different modes of disaggregation and definitions of indicators. The absence of rudimentary data at the school and local level in many areas is often

viewed as a crisis, inhibiting the development of effective education planning, monitoring, programming and policy-making. So, the lack of current data on public school education is a problem for the effective management of secondary schools in Nigeria (Ogunode, Adah, Audu & Abubakar 2021).

Appointment of non-professionals to head educational institutions is another major challenge that has hindered education development in Nigeria. Research shows that the majority of people appointed to head the various educational establishments in Nigeria are not professionals in the field of education. For instance, EduCeleb.com (2019 in Gamelegi 2019) did a study and report that Nigeria's Ministers of Education (1960-2020) had 51 persons who have either been Minister or Minister of State for Education, 11 of them were women, 23 were teachers at various levels of education before their appointment, 15 of them studies education courses and practised that in their professional lives, 11 of them were involved in educational administration before the appointment. Ogunode (2021) noted that many of these school managers do not have the right leadership skills and leadership qualities to ensure effective management of schools. Some of these school managers do not possess the human relationship skills and teamwork skills to allow them to manage the various teachers under them. The inability to effectively manage the teachers and coordinate them well definitely will lead to management failure and school failure.

Findings

The paper reveals that poor funding, shortage of professional teachers, infrastructure facilities, insecurities, corruption, lack of current data for planning and appointment of non-professionals to head educational institutions are some of the major problems facing education in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper discusses the various problems hindering education development in Nigeria. The paper concluded that The paper reveals that poor funding, shortage of professional teachers, infrastructure facilities, insecurities, corruption, lack of current data for planning and appointment of non-professionals to head educational institutions are some of the major problems facing education in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of the study, the paper recommends an increment in the budgetary allocation to education, employment of adequate professional teachers, provision of modern infrastructure facilities, provision of adequate security in schools, deployment of technologies to curtail corruption in the education administration, generation of timely data for educational planning and appointment of professional and qualified persons to head educational institutions.

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